

Sample 09a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0315
{Fe}	35.2
{Ca}	11.9
{Si}	11.0
{Si, Ca HiP}	5.5
{S, Ca}	3.8
{Al, Si}	3.5
{Si, S, Ca}	3.4
{Al, Ca}	3.2
{Ca, Fe}	2.9
{Si, Ca LoP}	2.7
{Mg, Si}	1.9
{Si, Fe}	1.7
{Mg, Fe}	1.6
{Al, Si, Ca}	1.2
{Mg, Ca}	1.2
{Mg}	1.0
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.8
{Al, S, Ca}	0.6
{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.5
{Na, S}	0.5
{Mg, S, Ca}	0.5
{Mg, Al, Si, K}	0.5
{Al}	0.5
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.3
{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.3
{Al, Si, K}	0.2
{Al, Fe}	0.2
{Mn}	0.2
{Na, Si}	0.2
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.2
{Mg, Si, S}	0.2
{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.2
{Na, Al, Si}	0.2
{S, Fe}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	10.1
Pellet	4.0
Ore preparation undifferentiated	15.9
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.2
Ore / hot metal	5.6
BOF converter slag	8.4
BOF converter slag slopping	1.4
Slag BOF converter or desulph	4.1
Desulph slag	0.4
Ca-aluminate slag	3.3
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	2.3
Olivine flux	1.2
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	3.3
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.4
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.2
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.3
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.1
Coal and cokes or soil	8.5
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	9.4
Carbon rich - other	8.8
Cement or BOF converter	1.3
Cement	0.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	4.8
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	4.4
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.3
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.1
Unassigned other	0.9

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	30.1
Site - ore / hot metal	5.6
Site - slag	17.7
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	3.5
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	3.3
Site - flux / refractory	0.4
Site - refractory	0.5
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.1
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	8.5
Site - carbon-rich other	9.4
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	8.8
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.3
Urban	0.3
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	4.8
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	4.4
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.4
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/o partial chloride cover)	1.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 09b

Sample 09b

Greyscale Image

141 μ m

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.1075
	{Fe}	29.7
	{Ca}	14.4
	{Si}	12.3
	{Si, Ca HiP}	6.6
	{Al, Ca}	4.5
	{S, Ca}	4.0
	{Si, Ca LoP}	3.4
	{Al, Si}	3.3
	{Si, S, Ca}	3.0
	{Ca, Fe}	2.8
	{Mg, Si}	1.5
	{Mg, Fe}	1.5
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.4
	{Mg}	1.3
	{Si, Fe}	1.1
	{Mg, Ca}	1.0
	{Al, S, Ca}	0.8
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.8
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.7
	{Al}	0.6
	{Na, S}	0.4
	{Mg, S, Ca}	0.4
	{Al, Cl}	0.3
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Al, Si, K}	0.2
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Mg, Si, S, Ca}	0.2
	{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.2
	{S}	0.2
	{Al, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
	{Ti}	0.1
	{S, Fe}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	7.2
Pellet	1.2
Ore preparation undifferentiated	12.9
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	3.9
BOF converter slag	9.9
BOF converter slag slopping	1.8
Slag BOF converter or desulph	2.7
Desulph slag	0.5
Ca-aluminate slag	2.8
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.2
Olivine flux	0.4
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	3.2
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.9
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.4
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.1
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	9.0
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	11.4
Carbon rich - other	18.8
Cement or BOF converter	1.7
Cement	0.1
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.5
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.3
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.5
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	4.3
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	3.3
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.2
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.6

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	21.4
Site - ore / hot metal	3.9
Site - slag	17.7
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.6
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	3.2
Site - flux / refractory	0.9
Site - refractory	0.4
Site - scrap	0.1
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	9.0
Site - carbon-rich other	11.4
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	18.8
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.7
Urban	1.3
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	4.3
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	3.3
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.2
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.6

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Greyscale Image

141 μ m

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.1075
	{Fe}	29.7
	{Ca}	14.4
	{Si}	12.3
	{Si, Ca HiP}	6.6
	{Al, Ca}	4.5
	{S, Ca}	4.0
	{Si, Ca LoP}	3.4
	{Al, Si}	3.3
	{Si, S, Ca}	3.0
	{Ca, Fe}	2.8
	{Mg, Si}	1.5
	{Mg, Fe}	1.5
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.4
	{Mg}	1.3
	{Si, Fe}	1.1
	{Mg, Ca}	1.0
	{Al, S, Ca}	0.8
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.8
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.7
	{Al}	0.6
	{Na, S}	0.4
	{Mg, S, Ca}	0.4
	{Al, Cl}	0.3
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Al, Si, K}	0.2
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Mg, Si, S, Ca}	0.2
	{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.2
	{S}	0.2
	{Al, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
	{Ti}	0.1
	{S, Fe}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	7.2
Pellet	1.2
Ore preparation undifferentiated	12.9
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	3.9
BOF converter slag	9.9
BOF converter slag slopping	1.8
Slag BOF converter or desulph	2.7
Desulph slag	0.5
Ca-aluminate slag	2.8
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.2
Olivine flux	0.4
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	3.2
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.9
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.4
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.1
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	9.0
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	11.4
Carbon rich - other	18.8
Cement or BOF converter	1.7
Cement	0.1
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.5
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.3
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.5
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	4.3
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	3.3
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.2
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.6

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	21.4
Site - ore / hot metal	3.9
Site - slag	17.7
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.6
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	3.2
Site - flux / refractory	0.9
Site - refractory	0.4
Site - scrap	0.1
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	9.0
Site - carbon-rich other	11.4
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	18.8
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.7
Urban	1.3
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	4.3
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	3.3
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.2
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.6

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 09c

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0085
{Fe}	35.1
{Ca}	13.2
{Si}	10.4
{Si, Ca HiP}	5.2
{Al, Ca}	4.5
{S, Ca}	4.0
{Ca, Fe}	3.6
{Si, Ca LoP}	3.5
{Si, S, Ca}	3.2
{Al, Si}	2.3
{Mg, Fe}	1.6
{Si, Fe}	1.4
{Al, Si, Ca}	1.3
{Mg, Si}	0.9
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.8
{Mg, Ca}	0.8
{Al, S, Ca}	0.7
{Mg}	0.7
{Al}	0.6
{Mg, Al, Si, K}	0.6
{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.5
{Mg, S, Ca}	0.4
{Na, S}	0.4
{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.3
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.3
{Al, Si, K}	0.3
{Mn}	0.3
{Na, Al, Si}	0.2
{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.2
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.2
{Mg, Si, S, Ca}	0.2
{S}	0.2
{S, Ca, Fe}	0.1
{Al, Fe}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	12.9
Pellet	2.6
Ore preparation undifferentiated	18.1
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.2
Ore / hot metal	5.0
BOF converter slag	9.7
BOF converter slag slopping	1.3
Slag BOF converter or desulph	3.9
Desulph slag	1.4
Ca-aluminate slag	4.3
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.3
Olivine flux	0.2
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	4.2
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.3
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.3
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.1
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	5.9
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	8.3
Carbon rich - other	7.6
Cement or BOF converter	0.2
Cement	0.0
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.6
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	5.3
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	4.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.6
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.1
Na-sulphate rich	0.2
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	1.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	33.9
Site - ore / hot metal	5.0
Site - slag	20.6
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.5
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	4.2
Site - flux / refractory	0.3
Site - refractory	0.3
Site - scrap	0.1
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	5.9
Site - carbon-rich other	8.3
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	7.6
Urban; rarely site - slag	0.2
Urban	0.6
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	5.3
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	4.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.6
Unknown	0.3
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	1.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels